

1 **TNF superfamily modulation in stricturing and penetrating Crohn's Disease.**

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7 Monoclonal antibodies that target soluble and membrane bound TNF alpha are gold standard therapies in
8 the inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease. TNF alpha belongs to a large family of immunoactive
9 ligands and receptors known as the TNF superfamily. We previously identified the TNF superfamily ligand
10 LIGHT (TNFSF14) as a stage-specific component or switch in the muramyl dipeptide gene expression
11 program in human monocytes and macrophage, and described the receptor for LIGHT, TNFRSF14, as a
12 defining transcriptional feature of the B3 (penetrating or fistulizing) phenotype in humans with CD. We
13 studied here the B2 and B3 ileal fibroblasts transcriptome to identify in an unbiased fashion TNF
14 superfamily genes whose expression identified the B2 and B3 phenotypes. We report the identification of
15 TNF superfamily ligands TNFSF15 and TNFSF4 as genes whose expression defines the stenotic B2
16 phenotype. In addition to TNFRSF14, expression of TNFRSF25 defined the penetrating (fistulizing) B3
17 phenotype.
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